

Security and Privacy Issues in Cloud, Fog and Edge Computing

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Abstract- *A new computer paradigm known as cloud computing entered the world with the introduction of technologies like the Internet of Things and 5G. The primary platform for data warehousing and processing is now cloud computing. Nevertheless, using the cloud to store data comes with its own set of difficulties and security issues. However, as more data is created from each device, the old cloud computing model is no longer able to solve issues like excessive latency, bandwidth restrictions, and resource shortages. Consequently, to address the issues with the former at or near the device, new computational paradigms like edge and fog computing are recommended. Both of these paradigms offer memory storage and compute possibilities that are close to the device itself. No system is flawless, despite its benefits. In this essay, I outline the various privacy and security issues that all three computing paradigms have, along with the remedies that have been suggested.*

Keyword: *Cloud Computing; Edge Computing; Fog Computing;*

1.0 Introduction

Over the past ten years, cloud computing [1] has become the top platform for storing and processing enormous volumes of data. It has spread into a number of sectors, including manufacturing, real estate, banking, healthcare, and education. Businesses send data to the cloud rather than storing it locally. As new technologies like 5G and IoT arise, traditional cloud computing is losing its ability to manage problems like excessive latency, resource allocation, and bandwidth limitation. A Cisco Global Cloud Index research estimates that by 2019, IoT devices would produce over 500 ZB of data [2]. IoT devices and smart apps increasingly leverage cutting-edge technologies like edge and fog computing for data management [3].

With the use of edge computing, data from IoT devices can be handled on or very close to the actual device. Instead of being handled at the main cloud data centre, the data is processed close to the device. All of the edge devices subsequently transmit the received data to the cloud storage repository.

In a decentralised computing environment known as fog computing, data, compute, storage, and applications are distributed between the data source and the cloud. The advantages and power of the cloud are brought closer to where data is created and used through fog computing. It's comparable to edge computing [4,5].

The terms edge computing and fog computing are interchangeable since both entail a middle level of computation and storage. The location of computing is the main distinction between the two. In a fog computing environment, the Local Area Network (LAN) acts as a gateway, but in an

edge computing environment, smart devices such as Programmable Automation Controllers carry out the computing (PACs).

The paper's outline is as follows: The architecture of cloud computing, privacy and security issues, and possible remedies are all covered in Section 2. Sections 3 and 4 cover edge computing and fog computing in the same way that section 2 does. A conclusion and discussion of the potential applications of computing technology are included in Section 5.

2.0 Cloud Computing

It alludes to the outsourcing of data processing and storage. Information hosted by a user is kept on a worldwide network of data centres rather than a local server. It is a subscription-based service, and in order to access the desired service environment, the customer must pay monthly costs. Users may access their information from anywhere with cloud computing, which also eliminates the need to buy pricey hardware for calculation and storage [1,3,4,6].

Its main features include resource allocation, flexibility, and broad network access (BNA). Users of BNA can access data from distant locations utilising common platforms like smartphones, laptop computers, and so on. Depending on tenant demand, resources are dynamically assigned. The ability of resources to scale up and down is referred to as elasticity.

Fig.1-Cloud Computing Architecture

Cloud computing threats are [6] :

1. Denial of Service (DoS) attack: In this attack, an unauthorised user attempts to block other authorised users from using the cloud service by flooding the network with messages in response to authentication requests from fake return addresses.
1. Cloud malware injection: A malicious service or virtual machine is introduced into the system during this assault. The user persuades the cloud that the newly implemented service is a genuine instance of the system.
2. Communication interception: Interception and exploitation of two users' conversation is possible.

As illustrated in Fig.1, it has three service architectures:

IaaS (Infrastructure as a Service): Users of this system can host their data on the hardware infrastructure through a virtual interface provided by the Cloud Service Provider (CSP). Users use their own operating systems (OS) and apps, and the deployed applications they use process, network, and store data.

Hardware resources like CPU, Memory, Disk, and Bandwidth are part of this design.

The following security concerns exist in this architecture:

1. The inability to keep track of cloud activities and applications.
2. Illegal access to sensitive data.
3. Data theft by an evil system user.
4. Host machine monitoring of virtual machines.
5. Remotely seeing a virtual machine through an another virtual machine.

Security issues in this architecture are addressed by the following solutions:

1. Network monitoring
2. Installation of firewalls
3. Network segmentation

Platform as a Service (PaaS): Users can create, test, launch, and manage apps using this system. Users are provided with a base operating system, certain development tools, and the infrastructure they need to create applications. Resources like storage and software frameworks are controlled here, as seen in the picture. The architecture of this system has the following security flaws:

1. CSPs don't use a secure software development approach.
2. In the event of a system failure or outage, recovery and backup
3. Insufficient Service Level Agreement clauses (SLA)
4. Legacy apps given by vendors

Security issues in this architecture are addressed by the following solutions:

1. Policy encapsulation for access control.
2. On top of the operating system, there is an additional layer known as the Trusted Computing Base (TCB), which is a collection of secure files.
3. Admission request authorization enforcement.

SaaS (software as a service): All of the system's infrastructure, operating system, and applications are supplied by cloud vendors. On-demand software is another name for it. Users can access the software via the web by purchasing a subscription. Users can use a web browser to access its services .

The following security concerns exist in this architecture:

1. The inability to consistently uphold compliance norms.
2. Lack of ability to assess CSP activities.
3. Insufficient authentication and authorization.
4. Data losses and breaches.

The following solutions deal with security vulnerabilities in this architecture:

1. User data encryption
2. Recovery services
3. Spam and malware protection for email
4. Backup of user data in the event of a system outage

3.0 Fog Computing

Fog computing, also known as fogging, is a type of cloud architecture where the data source and the cloud are separated by an intermediary layer. In fog computing, it is carried out at fog nodes, which gather data from various edge devices. Its main characteristics include mobility assistance, real-time interaction, reduced latency, awareness of the edge position, heterogeneity, and interoperability. The top edge nodes in fog computing are chosen at the network edge. Reduced latency and support for real-time communication are provided by these nodes. Together, fog nodes can offer services. The migration of the edge identity to a new host location is facilitated by fog nodes [6,7,8, 17, 18].

Fig. 2 shows a three-tiered building. The lowest layer is made up of edge devices like sensors, actuators, cars, or data-generating apps. At the second tier, above the edge devices, fog nodes are positioned to gather data from several edge devices. The fog servers use transport layer technologies like WiFi or Bluetooth to gather information from the edges. They serve as a two-way bridge between edge devices and the cloud and react instantly to requests from the edges. Fog nodes frequently consist of routers or base stations. The top layer is the cloud data centre, which gets its data from fog nodes.

Fog computing has come under criticism in various ways [7]:

1. DoS (denial-of-service) attacks
2. Attacks using virtual machines
3. Side-channel attack: Information about the device's cryptographic methods is gathered in order to reverse-engineer its encryption.
4. Session hijacking: Intercepting and taking control of a user session to get access to user information and services

Notwithstanding the benefits of fog, there are certain privacy and security issues, specifically:

1. Minimal Network Exposure
2. Inefficient assault detection techniques
3. No data collecting that is user-selective.
4. Issues with virtualization
5. Issues with multitenancy
6. Problems with evil fog nodes

These are some fog computing solutions [8]:

1. UBP using the Decoy method
2. Data encryption
3. virtual machine monitoring, and
4. Modified decoy technique: This variation of the original decoy approach gives the malevolent user bogus data and phoney nodes. Hidden batch files track these users' identities, including their Mac addresses, when they run the false programmes.

5. The TRM (Trusted Platform Module): Here, the cloud and edge share an additional root key, and the cloud can only access the data that the key has been used to protect. The cloud cannot access the remaining data.

Fig-2.-Fog Computing Architecture

4.0 Edge Computing

An edge computing paradigm [5,9, 18] prevents data from smart devices or sensors from being transferred to the cloud by storing it locally or on the device. Because it offers real-time data computation without delay, it is preferred to conventional cloud computing. Moreover, it facilitates quicker processing, quicker response times, and less network traffic. The level of security of the data is increased by the edge device's capacity to filter out sensitive data before transmitting it to the cloud centre. The term "edge" refers to any piece of hardware that connects a sensor to a cloud.

Reduced latency and lessened bandwidth restrictions are two of edge computing's key characteristics. Reducing the impact of a location's restricted bandwidth at a location involves moving the workload closer to the user. Only a few edge computing applications include data analytics, real-time monitoring, Network Function Virtualization (NFV), and network monitoring [9,10]. Running NFV on edge layers increases productivity and lowers costs. On the device itself, device data can be processed, and a compressed version of the data can be delivered to the central cloud. Fig.3 illustrates how the data sources in the edge computing architecture comprise the lowest level of the structure. These data sources can come from third-party systems, sensors, actuators, or appliances. These data sources use any transport layer protocol to exchange data with a nearby edge gateway using IoT protocols on the device or close by. These edge gateways pre-process the accumulated data before delivering it to the cloud. They act as an additional layer of defence against unauthorised access from other persons or devices.

Among the edge computing threats are:

1. **Eavesdropping:** An unscrupulous user can monitor the network while concealing its existence in order to collect user data.
2. **Data tampering attack:** The hacker can alter the data that is stored or that is delivered during communication.
3. **DoS (denial-of-service) attacks**

Despite the advantages, it has certain privacy and security problems, including [5,9,10]:

1. Insufficient security credentials make the system vulnerable to people who wish to do harm.
2. Insecure connection between devices.
3. Data backup and recovery in the event of a system breakdown.
4. Restricted network visibility.
5. Late reception and deployment of upgrades.
6. No user-selective data collection.

Fig.3-Edge Computing Architecture

The following are edge computing remedies:

1. Provide the same level of security on all edge nodes as the network.
2. The user will receive ongoing network monitoring and visibility through an interactive interface.
3. Data encryption and access control
4. Intrusion Detection System (IDS): It notifies the user when it discovers unauthorised access to the system.
5. A hardware performance monitor and lightweight cryptography methods
6. Using the decoy technique and user behaviour profiling (UBP) Users' general behaviour is tracked and preserved, and if there is a deviation from the anticipated behaviour, the user will receive false information.

Difference between cloud, fog and edge computing [11]

Parameter	Edge Computing	Fog Computing	Cloud Computing
Latency	Very Low	Low	High
Geo Distribution	Distributed	Distributed	Centralized
Response Time	Seconds to minutes	Miliseconds	Minutes,Days
Computing Power	Limited	Limited	High
Location of Data Processing	At Device Itself	At Fog Nodes Located at Lan Network	Within Internet
Interoperability	Low	Low	High

5.0 Applications of Cloud Computing, Fog Computing, Edge Computing:

Google Docs and Office 365 are two instances of the versatility and potential of cloud computing. Both Microsoft 365 and Google Documents are available online.

Examples of typical fog computing applications include smart grids, smart cities, smart buildings, automobile networks, and software-defined networks.

The device on your wrist and the computers analysing intersection traffic patterns are two examples of how edge computing is already in use all around us. Other uses include optimising streaming video and optimising smart utility grid analysis, safety monitoring of oil rigs, and drone-assisted agriculture management.

Some use cases of Fog Computing in the literature pertain to resource management as the service level objective (SLO):

Ref	Aim	Objective parameters	Results
[12]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A dynamic resource provisioning system for fog micro datacentres is suggested. It allocates resources in a dynamic manner to accommodate the changing workload requirements of fog applications because of changes in consumer demand, traffic patterns, the environment variations, or other factors. It employs a predictive algorithm for estimating the resource demands, and a feedback control mechanism to adapt resource allocation in response to changes in the workload in real time. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Service Oriented Probability (SOP) Average Overall Probability (AOP) Resources 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Evaluates against various levels of Cloud Service Customers, from level 1 through level 5 SOP varies from 0.1 to 0.5, increasing by 0.1 in each level AOP varies between 0.2 to 0.7, with 0.7 for CSC 3 Resources estimated as 52, 47, 21, 45 and 27 for different levels of CSCs respectively. The results shows that it may successfully cut reaction time and resource usage while ensuring excellent service availability.
[13]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> An IoT-based dynamic resource estimation and pricing mechanism for the Fog Computing Micro Datacentre (FCMD). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Service Oriented Probability (SOP) Average Overall Probability (AOP) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Evaluates against various levels of Cloud Service Customers, from level 1 through level 5 SOP varies from 0.1 to 0.5,

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maximises revenue production while minimising resource allocation and energy use. • It uses dynamic pricing methods to improve resource allocation and a Markov process-based methodology to estimate the resource needs of IoT devices. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Average Resources 	<p>increasing by 0.1 in each level</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AOP varies between 0.1 to 0.7, with 0.7 for CSC 3 • Average resources estimated as 27, 59, 26, 62 and 50 for different levels of CSCs respectively. • The findings shows that it beats other current models in terms of resource utilisation and revenue creation.
[14]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • a situation in which computations in a software-defined embedded system backed by fog computing are carried out on either embedded devices or computation servers and task images are saved on a storage server. • To make the process easier to manage, it is suggested to use an effective work scheduling and resource management strategy with rapid task completion, which addresses three issues: task scheduling, resource management, and balancing I/O interrupt requests across storage servers. They are taken into account together and developed as a mixed-integer nonlinear programming problem. • In order to improve computation efficiency, the algorithm, fog computing assisted software-defined embedded system (FC-SDES), is modified by incorporating a three-stage job completion time minimization technique. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Request rate • Computation Service Rate (CSR) • Storage Service Rate (SSR) • Transmission Latency 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The task completion time (TCT) is an increasing function of task arrival rate that varies from 1.7 to 2.7 for the proposed algorithm • Because more requests can be processed on the client side at a higher processing speed as the client server rate rises, the TCT is a decreasing function of the CSR. This results in a reduction in computing time. • The proposed “Joint” algorithm takes less response time when measured for SSR • With mapping, the average task completion time is over 68.97% faster than it would be without mapping.
[15]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A low-cost resource management method for a medical cyber-physical system backed by fog computing (FC- 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of users • arrival rate • Number of base 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Measure the efficiency of the two phase algorithm against the greedy approach • The results of the two-phase

	<p>MCPS)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Integrates medical devices and software applications to improve patient safety and treatment efficacy. To reduce computational complexity, they designed the resource management problem into a mixed-integer nonlinear programming (MINLP) model, which is then linearized as a mixed-integer linear programming (MILP) problem. Offers a low-complexity, two-phase LP-based heuristic method and rigorously tests its effectiveness. 	<p>stations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Maximum delay The number of subcarriers in each BS 	<p>algorithm outperform the greedy algorithm when the user count is high, for example, 90.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The two-phase algorithm exhibits a noticeable advantage over the greedy algorithm when the maximum request rate is low, such as 0.1, but the performance gap between the two algorithms reduces after 0.6 Total costs of both algorithms decrease with increasing number of BS Total cost is a non-increasing function of the delay constraint The overall cost exhibits a decreasing trend initially, followed by convergence as the number of subcarriers increases.
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An application of Fog computing in the literature related to IoT Device's Data Security Management as the service level objective (SLO) in [16] offers an algorithm (DSMM) for secure data management in IoT devices using fog computing. For effective and secure data transfer, the approach uses the Density Control Weighted Election (DCWE) algorithm and Extensible Authentication Protocol (EAP). Based on its workload and proximity to the IoT device, the DCWE algorithm chooses the best Fog node for data processing, and EAP guarantees secured authentication between the Fog node and the IoT device. They evaluated their algorithm using parameters, Accuracy ratio and recall ratio (%), Performance ratio (%), Response time ration (%), Data processing time ratio and precision ratio (%) and Data security rate (%). They contrast their results with those obtained using currently used techniques, such as the Compressed and Private Data Sharing Framework (Cpds), the Privacy-Preserved Data Sharing Framework (PPDSF), Ant Colony Optimization with Multi Kernel Support Vector Machine Model (ACOMKSVM), and Block Chain Technology with Wireless Body Area Networks (BC-WBANM). In comparison to previous approaches, the suggested algorithm, called DSMM, has a data processing time ratio of 86.3%, data security of 98.09%, precision of 97.23%, performance of 92.21%, effective data authentication ratio of 94.91%, recall of 97.25%, and response time of 96.18%.

6.0 Conclusion

The Internet of Things (IoT) is a sector that is quickly growing. As data and data-generating gadgets become more prevalent, we will need to transition from antiquated computing techniques to cutting-edge ones. Fog and edge computing are starting to replace standard cloud computing for processing data from IoT devices. We will need to create new computation

methods while putting the security and privacy of user data first as more and more data becomes available. Cloud computing should primarily be replaced by edge and fog computing in the future. Research may be done to further reduce latency and bandwidth needs without compromising system security. The system should function independently after being initially set up to meet all the requirements.

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